

Family Instability as Correlate of In-School Adolescents' Deviant Behavior in Enugu State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background: Several deviant behaviors are perpetrated by adolescents especially those in school settings. Family context may predict adolescents' disposition regarding deviant behavior. This study looked at the connection between family instability and the deviant behavior of in-school adolescents. The relationship between family instability and adolescent deviant behavior after controlling for gender and school location effects was also examined in this study.

Methods and Materials: A correlation survey methodology was used in the study. Four hundred (400) high school students were chosen as the study's sample size. The instruments were the Deviant Behavior Variety Scale (DBVS) and Family Instability Questionnaire (FIQ). The internal consistency of the instruments was established using Cronbach Alpha statistics, the reliability coefficient value for the Deviant Behavior Variety Scale (DBVS) was 0.75; Family Instability Questionnaire (FIQ), 0.82.

Results: The findings revealed a significant positive relationship between family instability and deviant behavior among adolescents enrolled in schools, and this relationship remained significant after controlling for gender and school location effects. Male students were discovered to experience similar levels of family instability as females, but they manifested more deviant behavior than female adolescents. It was also found that urban adolescents reported more deviant behaviors than those in rural schools but adolescents in both locations reported similar exposure to family instability.

Conclusion: Parents should devote effort towards ensuring that the family is stable in all aspects. If that is ensured, in-school adolescents would have a growth-enabling environment to lead a better life and positively impact the family, school, and the wider society.

KEY WORDS

adolescents, deviant behavior, family instability, gender, school location

INTRODUCTION

Adolescents exhibit various kinds of behavior as they interact with environmental factors virtually every day; these behaviors can be social or deviant¹⁾. Socially acceptable behaviors are encouraged; on the contrary, deviant behaviors are unacceptable to society^{2,3)}. Deviant behavior includes both formal and informal violations of social norms⁴⁾. It also includes actions or behaviors that violate laws. Deviant behavior, then, is any behavior, idea, or emotion that goes against what is considered acceptable in society. It is any lifestyle that is contrary to societal expectations and personally hurtful. More so, there are various kinds of deviant behaviors such as cultism, drug abuse^{5,6)}, bullying, examination malpractice^{7,8)}, and sexual assaults⁹⁻¹¹⁾, among others. Deviant behaviors may be exhibited by children, adolescents, adults, or the aged¹²⁾, but this study focuses on adolescents. More so, there are adolescents within the school setting (in-school adolescents) and those outside the school setting (out-of-school adolescents) but this study focuses on in-school adolescents' deviant behavior. Adolescents as young people ought to adjust well to their environment, developing in all domains of human activities at quite an optimal rate. To achieve this, the role of the family cannot be undermined right from childhood stage to adolescence. Scholars have asserted that adolescence is a stage of storm and stress when adolescents are exposed to varying life challenges, especially those related to their

developmental processes^{13,14)}. Such aspects of development include the cognitive, emotional, social, and physical among others^{15,16)}.

Several deviant behaviors are perpetrated by adolescents especially those in school settings^{13,17,18)}. Prominent among in-school adolescents' deviant behavior is drug abuse^{5,19)}. The drugs that students often abuse include sedative, depressants, narcotics, and other psychoactive drugs¹³⁾. The United Nations for Drug and Crime reported that there were about 14.3 million drug users in Nigeria between the age ranges of 15 to 63 years, among which 3 million suffered from drug use disorder²⁰⁾. This confirms that adolescents are among the perpetrators of drug abuse in Nigeria.

The incidence of students who sneak out of school to abuse drugs in Nigerian schools²¹⁾. The UNDC also reported that about 1.55 million of these drug users are from the South-East geopolitical zone (Enugu inclusive) of Nigeria²⁰⁾. Drug abuse and other deviant behaviors like pilfering have been observed by the researchers in the study area. In addition to the foregoing, the UNDC further reported that there are 11 million cannabis users in Nigeria who needs drug counseling²⁰⁾. Although in-school adolescents abuse drugs in obscurity, away from the watch of the school authorities, such unfortunate behavior leads to poor academic achievement, fighting, bullying, poor interpersonal relationships, rape, truancy, and depression among others²²⁻²⁴⁾. Several factors may be related to adolescents' deviant behavior, such include peer pressure, poor school environment, personality, family factors, and social media among others

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others^{22,25-27}). However, this investigation looked at the relationship between unstable families and the deviant behavior of adolescents in Enugu State's schools. This is necessary as the family is the basic unit of society and the procreative organ of society. Hence, it is pertinent to investigate the association between the important system of the social unit on in-school adolescents' deviant behavior.

There are a lot of instabilities in contemporary society, such as political instability, economic instability, and family instability among other instabilities. Family instability is focused on because family is the foundation and cornerstone of society²⁸⁻³⁰. Hence, anything that happens in the family may have a probable relationship with the in-school adolescents' deviant behavior. Family instability is the result of modifications to parents' living situations and personal relationships, such as marriage, divorce, and the relocation of love partners²⁹. Family instability is the recurrent change that threatens the proper adjustment of the family members^{32,33}. In the context of this study, family instability is the various imbalances that are hurtful to family members tending toward maladaptive behavior. In contemporary society, unlike in the days of old, several parents do not have time for their family members, many parents now give a greater percentage of their attention to their careers, especially women who are supposed to be home-builders³³. Adolescents are therefore left to fend for themselves. Due to the loneliness which may accompany this, some adolescents have been victims of sexual assault⁴¹.

Several studies have been conducted on in-school adolescents' deviant behavior. Social factors increase adolescents' susceptibility to deviant peers³⁵. Family context may predict adolescents' disposition regarding deviant behavior²⁵. Family instability may be related to deviant behavior among children³⁶. The structure of a family may influence the students' addictive behavior^{37,38}. The prevalent atmosphere in a family is related to adolescents' deviant behavior³⁹. Prevalent family structure affects deviant behavior⁴⁰.

The exhibition of deviant behavior among in-school adolescents may differ by gender⁴¹⁻⁴³. Gender implies the masculine and feminine roles, responsibilities, duties, and expectations associated with males and females respectively within society⁴⁴. It is incontestable that there are peculiarities between a male and female child from childhood to adolescence and even adulthood. Such peculiarities may also play out to influence the relationship between family instability and in-school adolescents' deviant behavior in this study. To capture such influence, this study was moderated by gender. Male adolescents manifest deviant behavior more than female students²². On the contrary, it was reported that there is no significant difference in deviant behavior between adolescent males and females⁴⁵. Apart from gender, the school location of the adolescents either rural or urban may affect the relationship between family instability and in-school adolescents' deviant behavior. Operationally, school location is the nature of the geographic settlement where the adolescents' school is located. School location influences students' deviant behavior⁴⁶⁻⁴⁹. The relationship between family instability and adolescent deviant behavior after controlling for gender and school location effects was therefore examined in this study.

Objectives of the Study

To better understand the factors that contribute to in-school adolescents' deviant behavior, this study looked at family instability in Nsukka Education Zone, Enugu State. The study specifically aimed to determine the relationship between:

1. family instability and in-school adolescents' deviant behavior.
2. family instability and in-school adolescents' deviant behavior after controlling for gender.
3. family instability and in-school adolescents' deviant behavior after controlling for school location.

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were developed in response to the aforementioned study objectives and were validated at the significance level of 0.05.

There is no significant relationship between:

- H₀₁: family instability and in-school adolescents' deviant behavior.
 H₀₂: family instability and in-school adolescents' deviant behavior after controlling for gender.
 H₀₃: family instability and in-school adolescents' deviant behavior after controlling for school location.

Literature Review

Family Instability and Deviant Behavior

Family instability and juvenile delinquency were studied in Owerri Municipality in Imo State, Nigeria³⁶. The study's findings showed that delinquent behaviors may originate from unstable families³⁶. The study is relevant to the current study since it explored how family instability affects adolescents' behavior. In the Ado-Ekiti local government area of Ekiti State, Nigeria, the psychosocial factors that influence teenagers' recognized addictive behavior was investigated³⁸. The study's findings indicated that adolescents' addictive behavior is influenced by their familial environment and socioeconomic level³⁸. In Pontia District Johor of Malaysia, the effect of the home environment on the in-school deviant conduct of teenagers was examined³⁹. The study showed a strong connection between family dynamics, including parenting style, parental love, family conduct, religious affiliation, and deviant behavior³⁹.

Gender and Deviant Behavior

A study on the directionality between tolerance of deviance and deviant behavior in persistently anxious children in the United States was examined⁴⁵. The study's conclusions included the notion that substance abuse or conduct problem terminology rises with age. Furthermore, the outcome shows that there is no appreciable distinction between males and girls in deviant behavior⁴⁵. In a past study, the causes of deviant conduct among young people in Nairobi, Kenya's Njathaimi community were investigated⁴⁹. The study demonstrated that gender is unrelated to teenage deviant conduct. Among other things, the data showed that socioeconomic characteristics, including family stability or instability, were statistically significant to deviant behavior in the study area⁴⁹. A cross-sectional national study conducted in Europe looked into aberrant behavior among adolescents and the impact of family, school, and community⁵⁰. The data showed that every independent variable, except for family leisure, was significantly and to varying degrees connected with either unlawful downloading or hacking. It also showed that aberrant behaviors are linked to gender and age⁵⁰. Socioeconomic factors as predictors of adolescents' attitudes toward criminal activity were investigated in another study²⁵. The study's findings showed that teenagers' views regarding deviant behavior are influenced by socioeconomic settings, parental income, peer group influence, adolescents' gender, and age²⁵.

Location and Deviant Behavior

In the Obollo-Afor Education Zone in Enugu State, Nigeria, how parenting practices affected secondary school students' deviant behaviors were investigated⁴⁶. The investigation's conclusion showed that gender had an impact on students' abnormal conduct. It also revealed that students' deviant behavior is influenced by their school's location and that males are more likely than females to engage in deviant behavior. In addition, respondents from urban regions engaged in deviant conduct more frequently than those from rural areas⁴⁶. The roles of deviant peer affiliation and gender in bullying, victimization, and parental behavioral control of rural Chinese teenagers were examined in another research²². The results showed that parental behavioral management could not directly predict school bullying. It also showed that girls are more likely than boys to be affected by their rebellious classmates²².

This section included empirical studies that were conducted both inside and outside of Nigeria. Several of the reviewed studies revealed some elements of family stability or instability, such as family atmosphere, family structure, and family dysfunction among others. Despite the studies on the deviant behavior of adolescents at school, it has not been demonstrated whether this behavior is related to family instability, and if it is moderated by gender and school location, particularly in the context of Nigeria. It was also noted from the reviews that very few studies used the correlation survey design. These and other elements created the gaps that this study aimed to close.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

The investigation was conducted using a correlation survey research design. This became crucial since the researchers wanted to look into

Table 1: Descriptive analysis of DBVS by Gender and School Location

Gender	School location	Family instability categories	Mean	SD
Male	Rural	unstable family	37.05	4.099
		Total	37.05	4.099
	Urban	unstable family	38.36	5.231
		Total	38.36	5.231
	Total	unstable family	37.72	4.742
		Total	37.72	4.742
Female	Rural	stable family	30.00	3.112
		unstable family	36.29	4.164
		Total	36.21	4.195
	Urban	unstable family	37.00	4.719
		Total	37.00	4.719
		Total	37.00	4.719
	Total	stable family	30.00	3.112
		unstable family	36.72	4.516
		Total	36.69	4.529
		Total	36.69	4.529

the magnitude and direction of the association between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Adolescents' deviant behavior at school is the dependent variable, and family instability is the independent variable.

Participants

All 3,112 SS 2 students from the 61 high schools in the Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State, Nigeria [1,446 (47%) males and 1,666 (53%) females] make up the study's population. Population data were obtained from the 2021 Post Primary School Management Board, Planning, Research, and Statistics. Four hundred (400) SS 2 Students from the local schools were chosen as the study's sample size. Using the Taro Yamane formula⁵¹, a sample was taken from the general population. The minimum sample size required by the results was 354, hence, the researchers used a sample size of 400. The youngest participant was 14 years, while the oldest was 19 years. To spread the sample for the study over the education zone while considering the moderating variables, a multistage sampling procedure was used.

The researchers initially purposefully chose one rural and one urban settlement, Igbo-Etiti, and Nsukka, respectively. Due to the frequent terrorist assaults in the Local Government Area, Uzo-Uwani was excluded from the study. In the second step, a proportionate stratified random sampling procedure was employed to calculate the percentage of the sample for each LGA to ensure fair representation of school sites (rural and urban). As a consequence of the estimate, 303 (86%) and 97 (14%), in-school adolescents from urban and rural schools, respectively, were selected from the L.G.As of Nsukka and Igbo-Etiti. To account for gender, the sample for male and female in-school adolescents was subsequently drawn using the proportionate stratified random sampling technique as follows: Nsukka (Male = 139, 46%; Female = 164, 54%) and Igbo-Etiti, (Male = 49, 51%; Female = 48, 49%). In all, the total male and females were 188 (47%) and 212 (53%) respectively. In the fourth step, a purposeful sampling technique was used to choose eight schools from the Nsukka Education Zone, five from the Nsukka Local Government Area, and three from the Igbo-Etiti LGA, to administer the instruments in both rural and urban settings.

Procedures

A master's student from the University of Nigeria helped the researchers administer the instruments over two weeks in both urban and rural schools through direct delivery and retrieval technique. A brief introductory conversation was held before each participant received their questionnaire. Participants were informed of the purpose of the survey and politely requested to assist in completing the questionnaires' items. Each participant received a confidentiality guarantee and was informed that their opinions would only be used for the study (information will not be exposed to a third party). Only participants who provided their consent took part in the study.

Measures

To measure engagement in deviant behavior among adolescents enrolled in school, the researchers modified the Deviant Behavior Variety Scale (DBVS)⁵². The scale has 19 items and a Cronbach alpha of 0.83. The item statements include the following. During the last year, have you ever: been to school or class after drinking alcohol; lied to adults (e.g., family members, teachers, etc.); hit an adult (e.g., teacher, family, security guard, etc.); and damaged or destroyed public or private property (e.g., parking meters, traffic signs, product distribution machines, cars, etc.). The scale's validity was examined during the current investigation, and after being adjusted into a 15-item scale utilizing the four-point Likert scale stated below, a 0.75 reliability coefficient was obtained.

To measure family instability, the researchers developed a 15-item questionnaire named: Family Instability Questionnaire (FIQ). Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 points, Agree (A) = 3 points, Disagree (D), = 2 points, and Strongly Disagree (SD), = 1 points were the four-point Likert scale used to frame the questionnaire. The item statements included: I have witnessed my parents quarreling or fighting at home; I sometimes find it difficult to discuss my problems freely with my father; My parents sometimes find it difficult to provide for my school needs; I mostly take decisions independent of my parents among others.

The researchers gave the instruments to three experts for initial validation to determine the validity of the instruments. All of the specialists came from the University of Nigeria, Nsukka's Faculty of Education. Two of the experts were from the Department of Educational Foundations' Guidance and Counseling Unit, and the third expert was from the Department of Science Education (Measurement and Evaluation Unit).

The degree of internal consistency of the research instruments was assessed using the trial testing approach. Thirty (30) copies of the questionnaires were given to thirty (30) students at Community Secondary School in Agbani Education Zone, which is outside Nsukka Education Zone, to determine the internal consistency of the instruments. The responses from the students were examined using the Cronbach Alpha statistics. The fact that the instruments were polytomously scored made this necessary. The Deviant Behavior Variety Scale (DBVS) and the Family Instability Questionnaire (FIQ) both have reliability coefficient values of 0.75 and 0.82, respectively. As a result, the instruments are presumed to be dependable because the overall dependability coefficient value is 0.87.

Data Analytic Strategy

All of the variables' descriptive statistics, including gender, family instability, deviant behavior, and school location, were computed. To describe how inherent stability or instability of families cut across gender and school location, the FIQ was transformed from continuous scale to categorical variable, divided into two categories: stable and unstable families. Further, the mean and standard deviation was employed to analyze the FIQ and DBVS scores across gender and school location. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was utilized to test the first hypothesis in a simple linear regression model. Linear regression analysis was also conducted to examine whether association between family instability and the deviant behavior of in-school adolescents will exist after controlling for gender and school location effects. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was adopted to assess collinearity. The statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 26 and Jeffreys's Amazing Statistics Program (JASP) 16.3 were used for all analyses.

RESULTS

According to the study objectives and hypotheses of the investigation, the outcomes of the data analysis are reported as follows.

The results in Table 1 revealed that male adolescents in urban schools (38.36 ± 5.231) from unstable families reported more deviant behavior than their rural counterpart (37.05 ± 4.099). The table also revealed that female adolescents in urban schools (37.00 ± 4.719) from unstable families reported more deviant behavior than their counterparts in rural schools (36.29 ± 4.164).

Table 2 showed that male adolescents' (37.72 ± 4.74) than females (36.69 ± 4.53) reported more deviant behavior. Thus, ANOVA results showed that there was a statistically significant difference in in-school adolescents' deviant behavior between male and female participants, $F(1, 396) = 5.835, p = .016$, and $\eta^2 p = .015$. Male adolescents ($39.85 \pm$

Table 2: Descriptive and Univariate ANOVA results for study variables

Variables	DBVS					FIQ				
	Mean (SD)	<i>F</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	η^2p	Mean (SD)	<i>F</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	η^2p
Gender										
<i>Males</i> (<i>n</i> = 179)	37.72 (4.74)	5.835	1,396	.016	.015	39.85 (5.21)	.825	1,396	.364	.002
<i>Females</i> (<i>n</i> = 218)	36.69 (4.53)					39.40 (4.96)				
School location										
<i>Rural</i> (<i>n</i> = 179)	36.64 (4.16)	4.866	1,396	.028	.012	39.51 (5.14)	.178	1,396	.674	.000
<i>Urban</i> (<i>n</i> = 218)	37.55 (4.97)					39.68 (5.03)				
Mean (SD)										

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$; DBVS = Deviant Behavior Variety Scale, FIQ = Family Instability Questionnaire

5.21) reported similar exposure to family instability as their female counterparts (39.40 ± 4.96). ANOVA results showed that there was no statistically significant difference in reported experience of family instability between male and female participants, $F(1, 396) = .825$, $p = .364$, and $\eta^2p = .002$.

Table 2 also revealed that adolescents from urban schools (37.55 ± 4.97) exhibit more of in-school adolescents' deviant behavior than those from rural schools (36.64 ± 4.16). Thus, the ANOVA results showed that there was a statistically significant difference in in-school adolescents' deviant behavior scores between urban and rural participants, $F(1,396) = 4.866$, $p = .028$, and $\eta^2p = .012$. Table 2 also revealed that adolescents from urban schools (39.68 ± 5.03) also reported similar exposure to family instability as their rural counterparts (39.51 ± 5.14). Thus, the ANOVA results showed that there was no statistically significant difference in reported experience of family instability between urban and rural participants, $F(1, 396) = .178$, $p = .674$, and $\eta^2p = .000$.

Further analysis of the variables was conducted using simple linear regression to test the association between adolescent deviant behavior and unstable families. To guarantee that the assumptions of normality, linearity, multi-collinearity and homoscedasticity were not violated, preliminary studies were carried out. None of the VIF values indicated that the results of the regression could have been skewed by predictor collinearity. Family instability is positively correlated with in-school adolescents' deviant behavior, according to the estimated regression equation provided by the results, $F(1,395) = 62.99$, $p < .001$, with an $R = 371$ and R^2 of .138. As a result, we agreed with the alternate hypothesis which claimed that family instability is associated with adolescents' deviant behavior at school.

We controlled for gender and school location effects on the association between family instability and the deviant behavior of adolescents. The outcome demonstrated that there was a statistically significant relationship between family instability and in-school adolescents' deviant behavior after controlling for gender effect: $R = .388$, $R^2 = .151$, $F(1, 177) = 31.38$, $p < .001$, $\beta = .388$. The results showed that there was a statistically significant relationship between family instability and in-school adolescents deviant behavior after controlling for school location effect: $R = .391$, $R^2 = .153$, $F(1, 222) = 39.98$, $p < .001$, $\beta = .391$.

DISCUSSION

The findings demonstrated that there is a significant relationship between family instability and in-school adolescents' deviant behavior. By implication, the percentage of variation in the in-school adolescents' deviant behavior can be attributed to family instability. The finding corroborate with the discovery that family instability contributes to adolescent behavior³⁶. The result is similar to the finding that adolescents' behavior is influenced by family structure³⁸. In addition to the foregoing, previous finding reported that there is a significant relationship between the family atmosphere and deviant behavior³⁹. As family insta-

bility is related to deviant behavior, in-school adolescents, teachers and parents should be aware of this relationship.

More so, on gender moderation, male students were discovered to experience similar levels of family instability as females, but they manifested more deviant behavior than female adolescents. Further analysis upheld that the relationship between family instability and deviant behavior is statistically significant after controlling for gender effect. The finding supports a report that male and female adolescents display different levels of deviant behavior⁴⁰. The findings support a study that revealed a relationship between gender and adolescent attitudes toward deviant behavior²⁵. However, the finding contradicts a study which reported no significant difference in deviant behavior between males and females among adolescents⁴⁵.

It was also found that urban adolescents reported more deviant behaviors than those in rural schools but adolescents in both locations reported similar exposure to family instability. The significant relationship between family instability and deviant behavior remained after controlling for school location effect. This result is consistent with the claim that students from metropolitan areas are more likely to engage in deviant behavior than students from rural places⁴⁶. However, a previous investigation reported that parental behavioral management of adolescents peers has a substantial impact on the risk of being bullied in rural adolescents' compared to those in urban settlements²².

CONCLUSION

The outcome of this study established that there is a significant relationship between family instability and in-school adolescents' deviant behavior. This study also showed that the relationship between family instability and in-school adolescents' deviant behavior remained significant after controlling for gender and school location effects. In light of the foregoing, parents should devote effort towards ensuring that the family is stable in all aspects, especially urban-based parents. If that is ensured, in-school adolescents would have a growth-enabling environment to lead a better life and positively impact the family, school, and the wider society. Counselors should organize workshops on management of family stability and adolescent aggression at regular intervals to help parents and in-school adolescents.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None was declared.

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